

A simulation-based test to investigate interrater agreement for binary time series

Nadja Bodner^{1*}

¹Quantitative Psychology and Individual Differences Research Group, Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

* Corresponding author:

Nadja Bodner, Quantitative Psychology and Individual Differences Research Group, Faculty of Psychology and Educational Studies, Tiensestraat 102, 3000 Leuven, Belgium,
nadja.bodner@live.be.

Abstract

In observational studies, intensive longitudinal data are often collected by coding the presence/absence of behavior across time. Having a sufficiently high interrater agreement is then quintessential. Although a host of alternatives exist, Cohen's Kappa has been most popular ever since the measure has been introduced. In many cases, the obtained interrater agreement values are interpreted using the benchmarks provided by, for example, Landis and Koch. This is, however, problematic because of two reasons: First, the value of Cohen's Kappa (and many other interrater agreement measures) is impacted by the prevalence of the coded behavior. Second, these measures ignore the serial dependence that typically characterizes time series data. In this study, we aim to develop a test that allows interpreting a Kappa value in a given situation. Therefore, we will make use of the error rate committed by the coders during that coding process. For good coding reliability, we will, of course, aim for data where only a few mistakes have been committed. We will introduce a simulation paradigm that accounts for the serial dependence and relative frequency of the true data but also implements several mistakes corresponding with the benchmarks of Landis & Koch. On this data, we calculate Cohen's Kappa. This sampling distribution which contains a fixed number of mistakes is used for a one-sided significance test that investigates whether the values calculated on the rater-reported data are significantly higher than could be expected given the implemented error rate (and therefore are of acceptable quality).

Keywords: Cohen's Kappa, interrater agreement, binary time series, error rate permutation-based significance testing, shiny app

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Studying how psychological processes unfold over time has recently become highly popular in the behavioral sciences (Mehl et al., 2014). To this end, intensive time-series data are collected on the processes of interest (Hamaker et al., 2015). Next to using self-report (Houben et al., 2017; Myin-Germeys et al., 2018; Sels et al., 2016) or recording physiology through wearables (Allen et al., 2012; Bussmann et al., 2009), researchers recur to observational studies, where trained raters code the presence/absence of behaviors in small intervals. Coded behavior includes parenting behavior (Van Keer et al., 2019), attachment-related behavior (Bodner et al., 2019), or affective expressions in different contexts (e.g., family or dyadic interactions in the lab or in daily life; Granic & Patterson, 2006; Sheeber et al., 2012; Yuan et al., 2010).

The reliability of the obtained binary scores needs to be investigated and safeguarded. As for cross-sectional data, this is usually done by asking two or more raters to code the same fragment and computing an interrater agreement measure (Bakeman & Quera, 2011). Although a host of alternatives exist, Cohen's Kappa has been most popular ever since the measure has been introduced by Cohen (1960). In many cases, the obtained values are interpreted using the benchmarks provided by Landis and Koch (1977) and Fleiss (1971). Landis & Koch would consider values higher than .80 as almost perfect and Fleiss would consider .75 or above as excellent.

This all sounds straightforward. Yet, evaluating interrater agreement often turns out to be more thorny in practice, as we experienced ourselves. Specifically, we coded several parent and child behaviors in two-second intervals while the child was working on a task (Verhees et al., 2017). However, even after advanced training, the obtained kappa values for some behaviors remained very close to zero or were even negative, despite the proportion of agreement between raters being consistently high. The high proportion of agreement indeed points towards a low percentage of error committed by the raters. This is for some reason not reflected in the values of Cohen's Kappa.

When searching for explanations, we found two factors that accidentally and unintentionally impact the kappa values: the relative frequency of the behaviors, and the serial dependence in the time series data. First, relative frequency has been identified by many authors as a factor that impacts the value of Cohen's kappa. It is indeed already quite well documented (Bakeman & Quera, 2011; Feinstein & Cicchetti, 1990; Viera & Garrett, 2005) that Kappa and the proportion of agreement can strongly diverge for behaviors occurring only rarely because Kappa is negatively biased in such cases. Figure 1 (a) indeed reveals that behaviors with a low mean relative frequency often show low kappa values (inverse u-shaped lines systematically show lower values with high and low relative frequencies). Each of the lines represents data, on which a certain percentage of error has been committed by each rater. Unfortunately, the lines with the least error (upper lines) are the worst in this respect. According to Gwet (2002), this negative bias of Kappa stems from an overestimation of chance agreement. Although the problem has been reported for different types of (categorical) data, the problem is even more severe for binary data (Bakeman et al., 1997; Bakeman & Quera, 2011). This sensitivity of Kappa to relative frequency differences has been noticed in different contexts (Gardner et al., 2000), but still is often ignored in practice (Kuppens et al., 2011) as evidenced by the widespread practice to use benchmarks like those of Landis and Koch (1977).

Figure 1. Values of interrater agreement in dependence of relative frequency, serial dependence, and error rates.

Note. a) Cohen's kappa without serial dependence, b) Cohen's kappa with serial dependence. The lines present interrater agreement values calculated on simulated rater data for different percentages of committed error (error rate) at different relative frequencies. For a) no serial dependence has been implemented, b) simulated the true data with a serial dependence of $\rho_1|1 = .9$ and with a strong serial dependence in the error (segments of length 20; for details see simulation study)

The relative frequency paradox has been investigated thoroughly and some solutions have been proposed (e.g., Bakeman, 2022). Other interrater agreement measures have been proposed (e.g., Gwet, 2002; Wongpakaran et al., 2013). We investigate the other interrater agreement measures in more detail in Appendix 2. However, while some interrater agreement measures indeed depend less on the relative frequencies, most others have comparable flaws or show a reverse pattern (which makes it even more difficult to compare values). Anyway, none of the methods or measures deals with the second factor, serial dependence in the data.

This second factor, serial dependence, has not been discussed before in the context of the interrater agreement to the best of our knowledge. Indeed, Cohen designed Kappa to assess agreement in cross-sectional data. The independence of observations is therefore one of the underlying assumptions (Cohen, 1960). In time series data, however, this assumption will not hold, because the scores at one time point can be expected to depend on the scores at the previous time point.

In rater-reported data, this serial dependence is caused by the interplay of different mechanisms. On the one hand, the true behavior likely takes longer than one time unit. On the other hand, it is reasonable to also assume serial dependency within the rater's errors: a rater that misses the onset of a behavioral sequence may also fail to identify the presence of this behavior at the following time point(s). Both cases add up and cause that behavior is more likely reported at a certain time point if the behavior has already been reported at the previous time point. Put differently, the rater-reported data will consist of longer sequences of present behavior, either because it was truly shown or because the mistake hits several subsequent intervals. When putting together reports of different raters, every single disagreement is likely to result in a sequence of disagreements. As a consequence, Kappa values will become more extreme and the distribution of values will be wider (Bodner et al., 2021). This increases the uncertainty about the interrater agreement and makes it even more difficult to judge whether a certain kappa value is acceptable or not. Figure 1b depicts that the range (the dashed lines indicate the 1st and the 3rd quantile) broadens (compared to Figure 1a). We explore the impact of serial dependence in the data (on Cohen's Kappa and other interrater agreement measures) in detail in a simulation study provided in Appendix 1 & 2.

To summarize, the dependence of Cohen's kappa and other interrater agreement measures on relative frequency has been investigated thoroughly and several attempts have

been made to solve the problem, however, none of the solutions accounts for serial dependence in the data like it can be found in time series data. Therefore, we aim to propose a testing paradigm that accounts for both the relative frequency and the serial dependence and can so inform researchers whether the obtained values are acceptable given the properties of the data. Therefore we will make use of a hypothesis testing paradigm that investigates whether the obtained values are significantly larger than would be expected under the given properties. The test consists of three steps: First, we will simulate data that is similar to the reported data. Second, we will calculate the interrater agreement on the data. And finally, we will use the obtained sampling distribution for hypothesis testing. In what follows we will explain the three steps in more detail.

Simulation paradigm

The simulated data needs to meet three requirements to facilitate the comparison with the agreement of the rater-reported data: First, the generated data needs to reflect similar behavioral properties as the one on which the agreement measures were calculated. This is especially true for the relative frequency and the serial dependence in the true behavior because these properties impact the calculated kappa values. Second, we aim to implement a fixed error rate. This will later facilitate conclusions about whether the interrater agreement of the rater-reported data is acceptable on a certain level (i.e., significantly higher than would be expected for this error rate given the data properties). Third, we want to allow the implementation of serial dependence in the error committed by the rater.

These requirements are met by using a two-step procedure for the simulation of the data (see Figure 2). First, we simulate the underlying (in practice unknown) true data (expressing what happened) accounting for relative frequency and serial dependence. In the second step, we let the fictive raters commit errors. Therefore we generate error patterns that (a) change a fixed number of values in the true data (i.e. we use a fixed error rate), and (b) implement the error with serial dependency. We generate pairs of rater data by implementing different (rater-specific) error patterns on the same true data. These pairs are used to calculate the interrater agreement. Repeating this procedure (100 - 1000 times) results in an interrater agreement value distribution. This distribution can be used to test the hypothesis of whether the interrater agreement value calculated on rater-reported data, can be considered significantly higher than would be expected given the data characterizes and the error rate.

Figure 2.
Schematic representation of the generation process

Step 1: Generating True Data

The expression ‘true data’ denotes the underlying data that describes what happens in a situation. The ‘true data’ in real situations is, of course, unknown. The properties of the true data such as relative frequency and serial dependence have an impact on the interrater agreement. The simulated data should therefore have similar properties as the reported data. For this reason, we simulate the true data using properties from the reported data. Assuming that the relative frequency and the serial dependence of the true data impact the resulting agreement values, we aim to keep these parameters the same. Therefore we retrieve the relative frequency p_1^{true} and the conditional probabilities $p_{1|1}^{true}$ (conditional probability that behavior occurs given it occurred the moment before) and $p_{1|0}^{true}$ (conditional probability that behavior occurs given it did not occur the moment before) from the rater-reported data. Next, we simulate the true data by sampling from a Bernoulli distribution using these parameters. For the first time point, the Bernoulli probability equaled p_1^{true} . For the remaining time points, this probability amounted either to $p_{1|1}^{true}$, if the previous score was a one, or to $p_{1|0}^{true}$, if the previous score was a zero. This approach has the advantage that it results in true data with variation, even if always the same parameters are used (e.g., if we only have data from one rated behavior). This data generation method can also be used for simulation studies, when $p_{1|0}^{true}$ is estimated, based on the derivation in Bodner et al. (2021), as

$$p_{1|0}^{true} \approx \frac{p_1^{true} - p_1^{true} \cdot p_{1|1}^{true}}{1 - p_1^{true}}. \quad (1)$$

Step 2: Generating the rater-specific data

During the coding process, this true data is coded by multiple coders who, of course, make mistakes. When generating rater-specific data, we simulate a rater-specific error pattern and implement this on the true data. This error pattern needs to comply with two things: First, we want to implement a fixed error rate, that will make it easier to decide on which level the rater-reported data is acceptable. We realize this by implementing a fixed number of changes. Second, we aim to account for the impact of the error's serial dependence. To implement the serial dependence in the error we make use of the recently extensive validated (segment) shuffling approach (Bodner et al., 2021; Moulder et al., 2018). This comes down to cutting an auxiliary error file into segments and rearranging them, as we will explain in the next paragraph.

Figure 3 illustrates how we generate the error pattern with a fixed error rate and serial dependence. In the example, a simplified time series with 30 time points are used. The number of changes is calculated by multiplying the targeted error rate with the total length of the time series (in the example 20% of 30 time points, i.e., 6 points, are changed). The change candidates are indicated in an auxiliary time series (all 6 time points are indicated next to each other, with a random starting point). This auxiliary time series is then cut into segments and rearranged, which leads to groups of change candidate points being moved in groups (here the group of six is split into two groups of three). The length of the segments is a way to manipulate the serial dependence in the error: long segments (e.g., 20) result in a big serial dependence, while shorter ones (e.g., segment length of five) will lead to moderate or no serial dependence (segment length of 1). In our example, the auxiliary time series is cut into 6 segments each 5

time points long, and reshuffled. In our example, the 11th, 12th, 13th, 23rd, 24th, and 25th time point (or interval) is changed.¹

Figure 3. illustration of the shuffling approach.

Note: In the original time series we aim to implement an error rate of 20% which corresponds to changing 6 time points. The candidate time points for change are indicated in an auxiliary file (all in one sequence with a random starting point) which is then cut into segments and reshuffled. The indicated time points are changed in the original file.

¹ We did not take into account whether the true data showed behavior or not when implementing the error. As this might, however, change the relative frequency (in low relative frequency files it is more likely that 0s are changed to 1s which leads to a higher relative frequency), we also investigated a pattern that implements restrictions on the number of changes per code (e.g., change equally many 1s to 0s than 0s to 1s). The results can be consulted in Appendix 3.

A pair of rater data is simulated by implementing different error patterns² on the same true data. On each pair of rater data, that stems from the same true data, Cohen's kappa is calculated. If this is done for enough pairs (100-1000 pairs), we get a smooth distribution of values.

Hypothesis testing

The distribution of interrater agreement values calculated on the simulated rater data can be used for hypothesis testing: The distribution depicts the range in which values could be expected for data with the same relative frequency and serial dependence as the rater-reported data. Most importantly, we implemented a fixed error rate on the data. This gives us now the opportunity to use this distribution also as null hypothesis for hypothesis testing. We test whether the value calculated on the rater-reported data is significantly higher as could be expected with a certain error rate (given the properties of the data). In our example, we use a one-sided test that investigates whether the value from the rater-reported data is bigger than the 95th quantile of the distribution. Moreover, we use error rates that correspond to the Landis and Koch benchmarks (for the derivative see Appendix 4): 5.3% (almost perfect), 11.3% (substantive), and 18.4% (moderate). Eventually, an error rate of 18.4% per rater is probably not a value that indicates a suitable agreement. Therefore, we will not take this error rate further into account. In what follows, we will shed some light on the type 1 error and the power of this test.

Type 1 Error

To investigate the type 1 error of the test, we conducted a simulation study. Rater data pairs are generated using the simulation approach and tested with a test that uses the same error rate. We assume that about 5% of the data will falsely be identified as having a Kappa

² The error pattern may differ due to two mechanisms: First, the initial begin point of the sequence is randomly chosen. Secondly, the shuffling approach might rearrange the segments in a different way. Error rate and length of the segments are the same for both raters.

value that is significantly higher than would be expected given the data properties. We conducted the study crossing the following manipulations:

- Number of time points: 50, 100, 200, 500
- Error rates: 5,3%, 11,3% (corresponding to the .8 and .6 benchmarks of Landis& Koch)
The same error rates are used to generate the data and to test the data.
- Relative frequencies: 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5
- Serial dependence in true data simulated with conditional probability $p_{11i} = 0$ and 0.8/0.9³
- Serial dependence in error, simulated with segments of 1 (no), 5 (moderate), 10 (strong)

1000 simulated pairs of rater data (two raters) were tested all together with three tests (using the simulated, segmented and original approach⁴), each sampling distribution consisting of 500 samples.

³ .8 is used for the relative frequencies of .1 and .2, because in real data the serial dependence of lower relative frequencies are lower than for higher relative frequencies.

⁴ We display here only the simulated test, but the others can be consulted in the supplementary material.

Figure 4: Type 1 error for the test with an error rate of 5.3% and 11.3% in dependence of the length of the time series, the relative frequency, and the serial dependence.

Note: Type 1 error for the test with an error rate of 5.3% (left column) and 11.3% (right column). The results depict the percentage of rater data pairs that were erroneously classified as significantly higher than would be expected. The error rate in the rater data and in the test are the same. Different rows depict different time series lengths (50,100,200, 500 time points), within each panel different relative frequencies (.1, .2, .3, .4, .5; x-axis) and serial dependency conditions (symbols & line type) are used. For each condition, 1000 pairs of rater data were generated and tested with a sampling distribution of 500 values. The sampling distribution is generated using the simulation approach (the tests using the original and segmented approach can be consulted in Appendix 5).

Power

To investigate the power of the test, we conducted a simulation study. Rater data pairs with different error rates are generated using the simulation approach. We assume that a test using a higher error rate will have the power to detect that rater pairs with a lower error have a significantly higher kappa value than would be expected given the properties of the data. We assume that the test will indicate a bigger percentage of kappa values as significant as the error rate in the data deviates more from the test error rate. To investigate the dependence of other data properties we crossed the following manipulations:

- Number of time points: 50, 100, 200, 500
- Serial dependence in true data simulated with conditional probability $p_{11} = 0$ and $0.8/0.9^5$
- Serial dependence in error, simulated with segments of 1 (no), 10 (strong)

1000 simulated pairs of rater data (two raters) were tested all together with three tests (using the simulated, segmented and original approach⁶), each sampling distribution consisting of 500 samples.

- Error rates of 11.3%, 10%, 9%, 8%, 7%, 6%, 5% in the data are tested with 11.3% test
- Error rates of 5.3%, 4%, 3%, 2%, 1% in the data are tested with 5.3% test

⁵ .8 is used for the relative frequencies of .1 and .2, because in real data the serial dependence of lower relative frequencies are lower than for higher relative frequencies.

⁶ We display here only the simulated test, but the others can be consulted in the supplementary material.

Figure 5. Power for the test with an error rate of 5.3% in dependence of the error rate in the data (depending on the length of the time series, the relative frequency, and the serial dependence).

Note: Power for the test with an error rate of 5.3%. The results depict the percentage of rater data pairs that were correctly classified as significantly higher than would be expected. Different columns depict different relative frequencies in the true data frequencies (.1, .2, .3, .4, .5). Different rows depict different time series lengths (50,100,200, 500 time points), within each panel different error rates (.01, .02, .03, .04, .053; x-axis) and serial dependency conditions (symbols & line type) are used. For each condition, 1000 pairs of rater data were generated and tested with a sampling distribution of 500 values. The sampling distribution is generated using the simulation approach (the results of the same data tested with tests using the original and segmented approach can be consulted in Appendix 5).

Figure 6. Power for the test with an error rate of 11.3% in dependence of the error rate in the data (depending on the length of the time series, the relative frequency, and the serial dependence).

Note: Power for the test with an error rate of 11.3%. The results depict the percentage of rater data pairs that were correctly classified as significantly higher than would be expected. Different columns depict different relative frequencies in the true data frequencies (.1, .2, .3, .4, .5). Different rows depict different time series lengths (50,100,200, 500 time points), within each panel different error rates (.05, .06, .07, .08, .09, .10, .11; x-axis) and serial dependency conditions (symbols & line type) are used. For each condition, 1000 pairs of rater data were generated and tested with a sampling distribution of 500 values. The sampling distribution is generated using the simulation approach (the results of the same data tested by tests using the original and segmented approach can be consulted in Appendix 5).

Results:

The results reveal that the percentage of misspecified rater data pairs is close to 5% for all conditions. Lower relative frequencies seem to be prone to deflation of the value, while higher relative frequencies might result in slight inflation. The results suggest that more serial dependence in the error might lead to higher values (blue lines).

The power seems to be lower for shorter time series. Serial dependence in the error also seems to hamper power (especially if the time series are short). Lower frequencies seem to result in less power, especially if serial dependence in the error is present or/and if the time series is short. Overall the test shows the ability to detect that the underlying error rate is lower when the difference between the real value and the tested value is sufficiently large.

The shiny app

As completing all these calculations is a boresome endeavor, we developed a shiny app(application) that gives researchers the possibility to test their reported data. In what follows we will shortly describe the application, which is entirely based on the test paradigm as described above. The shiny app can be accessed at <https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/ppw-okpiv/researchers/u0090403/irrtest> . A more advanced version, ia available at <https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/ppw-okpiv/researchers/u0090403/shinymirror> .

Discussion

With this study, we propose a method to solve the problem that Cohen's kappa's value calculated on binary time series is impacted by relative frequency and also by the serial dependence of the true behavior and the committed errors. We introduced a simulation and hypothesis testing paradigm that is also available as a shiny app for easy implementation.

Indeed, Cohen's Kappa and many other interrater agreement measures (e.g., Krippendorff's alpha, etc.) are heavily impacted by the relative frequency and the serial dependency in the true behavior and by the serial dependence in the error, as we proof in several simulation studies (for Cohen's kappa see Appendix 1; for other interrater agreement measures see Appendix 2). Without further knowledge about those factors, it is very difficult to get an idea whether a calculated value of Cohen's kappa is acceptable or not. This is especially

true for variables with a very low or very high frequency (e.g., seldom shown behaviors in micro-coded interactions). These results raise serious doubts regarding popular rules of thumb (e.g., those of Landis & Koch, 1977) for classifying whether an interrater agreement value is sufficiently high or not. Any use of fixed thresholds that ignore the relative frequency and the serial dependence in the data seems not suitable to decide which time series are sufficiently well-rated. Having dismissed the rule of thumbs, the gap becomes obvious: We need a new method to decide whether a certain value of Cohen's kappa (or any other interrater agreement measure) is an indicator of sufficient high reliability of the rater(s).

We may conclude that raters are doing a good job if they make only a few mistakes during the rating process. If the observed data, leads thus to significantly higher interrater agreement values than does simulated data with a fixed error rate, we may assume that the data is acceptably well coded. Of course, we assume that all the other data characteristics are the same (especially, relative frequency and serial dependence).

To this end, we developed a test paradigm that first generates rater data with a fixed error rate (corresponding to the benchmarks of Landis and Koch). The generated rater data is adapted to the reported rater data in relative frequency and serial dependence. This allows us to compare the interrater agreement values calculated on the reported data to those from the simulation. Via hypothesis testing, it can be determined whether the reported values are significantly higher than the simulated values and therefore likely to have less rater error than the distribution. We consider these values sufficiently high to be coded following the corresponding agreement level. To apply this method more easily, we programmed it in a shiny app(lication) in which the researcher can read in the reported rater data needing investigation. We assume that this hand-tailored interrater agreement benchmarking is a big step towards more reliable interrater agreement decisions.

Strength and Limitations

This study is the first study to the best of our knowledge that investigates the impact of serial dependence on the interrater agreement in a systematic way. We propose a solution and provide researchers with an application that allows researchers to easily implement the paradigm on their data. The investigation of the test shows that type 1 error and power are acceptable, however, are for two reasons a little bit to the conservative side. First, we do only

accept values that are significantly higher than expected under a certain error rate given the properties of the data. This means that we would reject data that is most likely equal to the simulated data. Though this will definitively cast away cases that might still be acceptable (just to make sure that nothing slips through that is not acceptable), this might still retain more cases than a one-size-fits-them-all solution. Second, we noted that there are some indications that the type 1 error for low relative frequencies is deflated.

Another striking (but not surprising) result is that the power is lower when the time series are short, the relative frequency is low or a huge amount of serial dependence in the data is present. Combinations thereof are worse. These problems need a more thorough consideration, which often already needs to be addressed at the stage of planning and design.

A short length indicates that there is not enough information in the data to reliably code it. An interaction needs thus to be planned sufficiently long. One might be tempted to augment only the measurement time points (without making the interaction longer) to get longer time series. This, however, will not solve the problem because implementing more measurement time points on the same interaction will lead to a higher serial dependence, which then will again lead to lower power.

Variables that occur only rarely still form a problem for interrater reliability. Again the reason is that there is not much information in the corresponding time series. To this end, it is necessary to think thoroughly about the research question and which behaviors are pivotal for the study at hand. Coding many different behaviors, especially if they are mutually exclusive, will lead to fragmentation of the codes, resulting in some variables that only show a low frequency. Analyzing the sequences of rarely occurring variables is for this reason a difficult endeavor. We understand that many of these variables are indeed very meaningful as they might be valuable indicators, however, other methods of investigation might be more suitable in the case of rarely occurring variables.

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<https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/ppw-okpiv/researchers/u0090403/mirror>

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Appendix 1 – Simulation study 1: Investigating the impact of serial dependence

Study design

This simulation study aims to investigate how big the impact of serial dependence on the interrater agreement is. Therefore, we manipulate the serial dependence in the true data and the serial dependence in the error independently from each other. The true data was generated by drawing time point per time point from a Bernoulli distribution as described in the 'simulate' approach. As we already showed, the relative frequency of the observed behaviors has an impact on the calculated values. Therefore we also implemented different values for the relative frequency. Further, we expect that the fluctuation of possible values will rise with bigger error rates (giving more variability in which points are changed). To this end, we also implemented different error rates. More precisely we completely crossed the following manipulations.

- Relative frequency of the true data: p_1^{true} : .1, .2, .3, .4, .5
- Serial dependency in the true data: $p_{1|1}^{true}$: none (i.e., $p_{1|1}^{true} = p_1^{true}$), .5, .6, .7, .8, .9⁷
- Relative frequency in the error (error rate): .053, .113, .184
- Serial dependency in the error: segments of 1, 5, or 20 time points length

For each of the design cells, 1000 pairs of replicates were generated and analyzed. To avoid contamination of the results by sampling fluctuations we also chose to investigate time series of the length of 1000 time points. We stick to the big numbers here but investigate the impact thereof in Simulation Study X. The error was implemented in a random way as described in the main study.

Results

Figure A1.1 visualizes the simulation results for the three considered measures by presenting the obtained average interrater agreement scores per design cell, as well as the 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles. In each of these figures, the three represent different degrees of

⁷ Please note that for $p_1^{true}=.5$ the value $p_{1|1}^{true} = 0.5$ equals the non serial dependency condition.

serial dependency in the errors (absent, moderate, and strong serial dependence. Within a panel, the true relative frequency is represented on the x-axis ('the fences'). The different vertical lines within each group ('fences') represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (increasing from left to right). The committed error is coded by color. At a contingency value of .6, a dotted horizontal line is added as a reference (Landis & Koch, 1977, consider values between .61 and .80 as substantial interrater agreement).

Based on Figure A1.1, we again clearly see that the true relative frequency impacts Cohen's Kappa, in that lower frequencies go hand in hand with lower Kappa values (see also Cousineau & Laurencelle, 2017).

Figure A1.1.
Cohen's Kappa as functions of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and randomly committed errors.

Note: a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (segment length of 1 time point) and b) presence of a moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (segments are 5 time points long) c) strong serial dependence in the committed errors (segments have a length of 20 time points). Within each panel, each group of vertical lines represents the same true relative frequency as indicated on the x-axis and the same error relative frequency (yellow:0.053, orange:0.113, red: 0.184). The different lines within each group represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (none, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9). Each vertical line indicates the range of the results (with a fixed relative frequency, serial dependency, and error rate), while the horizontal dash marks the mean of the results.

First, our investigations demonstrate that serial dependence intensifies the insecurity over values. The serial dependency in the true behavior (different vertical lines within the groups) has the most severe impact on low frequencies. This can easily be discerned from the increasing length of the intervals (vertical lines in the 'fences') within the most left group

($\rho_1=1$). If the error shows serial dependency, the effects of the two types of serial dependency mutually reinforce each other, yielding wider intervals.

We may thus conclude that all three data characteristics (relative frequency and both types of serial dependence) impact the interrater agreement values and their precision, though there are some differences between the measures. Using a fixed threshold to discern which values represent an acceptable interrater agreement seems thus problematic, especially for time series (with their presence of serial dependence).

Appendix 2: Study 2: Investigation of the behavior of alternative interrater agreement measures

In this part, we will introduce additional measures of agreement and explain how they are calculated with a real data example (Verhees et al., 2017). We also conducted the simulation study (Appendix 1) for the following interrater agreement measures:

- Brennan-Prediger Coefficient
- Gwet's AC
- Krippendorff's alpha (Krippendorff, 1970)
- Bangdiwala's B (Munoz & Bangdiwala, 1997)
- Yule's Y (Yule, 1912)
- Jaccard (Jaccard, 1901, 1912)
- Corrected Jaccard index (Bodner et al., 2019)
- Fleiss Kappa (Fleiss, 1971)

Figure A2.1. Real Data of two coders coding the same data.

Brennan-Prediger coefficient (Brennan & Prediger, 1981; Holley & Guilford, 1964)

The Brennan-Prediger coefficient BP ranges between -1 and 1. It corrects for chance agreement by applying a linear transformation to the proportion of agreement which intends to shift chance agreement to 0: The correction does not depend on the shown behavior, but on the number of codes (for binary data the correction term is thus 0.5).

$$BP = \frac{P_a - .5}{1 - .5}$$

We calculated the Brennan-Prediger coefficient using the `bp.coeff.raw`-function from the R-package 'irrCAC'. For our example, the Brennan-Prediger coefficient equaled .8.

Figure A2.2. Brennan-Prediger coefficient as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency.

Note: Brennan-Prediger coefficient as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and the committed errors. a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (Segment of length 1), b) presence of moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (Segments of length 5), and c) presence of strong serial dependency in the committed error (segments of length 20). Within each panel, the true relative frequency is represented on the x-axis and the error relative frequency is color coded. The different lines within each group of intervals represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (increasing from left to right).

Gwet's AC

Gwet's AC is given by

$$AC = \frac{P_a - e(\gamma)}{1 - e(\gamma)}$$

For Gwet's AC the expected agreement by chance $e(\gamma)$ is computed in yet another way:

$$e(\gamma) = 2 \cdot \frac{p_1(1) + p_2(1)}{2} \cdot \frac{p_1(0) + p_2(0)}{2}$$

We used the `gwet.ac1.raw`-function from the R-package 'irrCAC' to compute the AC values.

Gwet's AC amounted to .8845 for our example.

Figure A2.3. Gwet's AC as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency

Note. Gwet's AC as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and the committed errors. a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (Segment of length 1), b) presence of moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (Segments of length 5), and c) presence of strong serial dependence in the committed error (segments of length 20). Within each panel, the true relative frequency is represented on the x-axis and the error relative frequency is color coded. The different lines within each group of intervals represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (increasing from left to right).

Krippendorff's alpha (Krippendorff, 1970)

Krippendorff's alpha ranges from -1 to 1 with 0 indicating the chance level. We calculated Krippendorff's alpha using the `krippen.alpha.raw`- function from the R-package 'irrCAC' (version 1.0). In our example we get $\alpha = 0.258$.

Figure A2.4. Krippendorff's alpha as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency

Note. Krippendorff's alpha as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and the committed errors. a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (Segment of length 1), b) presence of moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (Segments of length 5), and c) presence of strong serial dependence in the committed error (segments of length 20). Within each panel, the true relative frequency is represented on the x-axis and the error relative frequency is color coded. The different lines within each group of intervals represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (increasing from left to right).

Bangdiwala's B (Munoz & Bangdiwala, 1997)

Agreement between two observers:

$$B = \frac{\sum n_{ii}^2}{\sum n_{i.} * n_{.i}}$$

Thus the sum of quadrats of the main diagonal is divided by the sum of the product of the corresponding marginal frequencies. Bangdiwala's B varies between 0 (no agreement) and 1 (perfect agreement).

We calculated Bangdiwala's B using a self-programmed function (see OSF). In our example B = 0.8955

Figure A2.5. Bangdiwala's B as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency

Note. Bangdiwala's B as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and the committed errors. a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (Segment of length 1), b) presence of moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (Segments of length 5), and c) presence of strong serial dependency in the committed error (segments of length 20). Within each panel, the true relative frequency is represented on the x-axis and the error relative frequency is color coded. The different lines within each group of intervals represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (increasing from left to right).

Yule's Y (Yule, 1912)

Agreement between two observers:

$$Y = \frac{\sqrt{ad} - \sqrt{bc}}{\sqrt{ad} + \sqrt{bc}}$$

Yule's Y is calculated as the radical of the product of the diagonal values minus the radical of the product of the off-diagonal values, divided by the radical of the product of the diagonal values plus the radical of the product of the off-diagonal values. We implemented our own code to calculate Yule's Y (see OSF), here we get $Y=1$.

Figure A2.6. Yule's Y as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency

Note. Yule's Y as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and the committed errors. a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (Segment of length 1), b) presence of moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (Segments of length 5), and c) presence of strong serial dependence in the committed error (segments of length 20). Within each panel, the true relative frequency is represented on the x-axis and the error relative frequency is color coded. The different lines within each group of intervals represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (increasing from left to right).

Jaccard (Jaccard, 1901, 1912)

Jac_{Obs} is calculated as:

$$Jac_{Obs} = \frac{n_{11}}{n_{11} + n_{10} + n_{01}}$$

where n_{11} denotes how many times the first behavior is followed by the second behavior in the next interval, n_{10} how many times the first behavior is expressed, but not followed by the second behavior, and n_{01} how many times the second behavior is shown, without being preceded by the first behavior? The Jaccard index ranges from 0 to 1. We calculated the Jaccard index using our function (see OSF). In our example $Jac_{Obs} = 0.1818$.

Figure A2.7. Jaccard index as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency

Note. Jaccard index as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and the committed errors. a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (Segment of length 1), b) presence of moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (Segments of length 5), and c) presence of strong serial dependence in the committed error (segments of length 20). Within each panel, the true relative frequency is represented on the x-axis and the error relative frequency is color coded. The different lines within each group of intervals represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (increasing from left to right).

Corrected Jaccard index (Bodner et al., 2019)

The corrected Jaccard similarity index is calculated as

$$Jac_{Cor} = \frac{Jac_{Obs} - Jac_{Exp}}{1 - Jac_{Exp}}$$

With Jac_{Obs} indicating the Jaccard similarity index as introduced above and Jac_{Exp} expressing the Jaccard value that we would expect if no systematic association was present, taking the relative frequencies of both behaviors, denoted by p_1 and p_2 , into account:

$$Jac_{Exp} = \frac{p_1 * p_2}{1 - (1 - p_1) * (1 - p_2)}$$

The correct Jaccard index ranges between -1 and 1 with 0 indicating the chance level. We calculated the Corrected Jaccard index using our formula (see OSF) for our example we got $Jac_{Cor}=0.1658$

Figure A2.8. Corrected Jaccard index as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency

Note. Corrected Jaccard index as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and the committed errors a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (Segment of length 1), b) presence of moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (Segments of length 5), and c) presence of strong serial dependence in the committed error (segments of length 20). Within each panel, the true relative frequency is represented on the x-axis and the error relative frequency is color coded. The different lines within each group of intervals represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (increasing from left to right).

Fleiss Kappa (Fleiss, 1971)

Fleiss' Kappa is a generalization of Scott's pi for several raters. In our case, we added a third rater, whose data was calculated the same way as those of the two other raters (thus based on the same original data implementing an independent error with the same characteristics as for the two other raters).

In our study, we calculate Fleiss' kappa using the 'fleiss.kappa.raw'- function from the 'irrCAC'- R package (version 1.0).

Figure A2.g. Fleiss' Kappa as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency

Note. Fleiss' Kappa as a function of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and the committed errors. a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (Segment of length 1), b) presence of moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (Segments of length 5), and c) presence of strong serial dependence in the committed error (segments of length 20). Within each panel, the true relative frequency is represented on the x-axis and the error relative frequency is color coded. The different lines within each group of intervals represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (increasing from left to right).

The differences between the different interrater agreement values often originate in the correction terms that are implemented on the different coefficients. The main purpose of these correction terms is to correct for agreement that is merely coming into existence by chance. Here we will take a look at the Brennan-Prediger coefficient and Gwet's AC. In our example, both implement lower estimates of chance agreement (.5 and .1340) than Kappa (.8610). As a consequence, the values of these measures are much closer to those of the proportion of agreement. These values, however, highly depend on the relative frequencies. Table 1 summarizes the formula for each of the discussed correction terms and gives two more examples. We did assume that the two raters code the behaviors with equal relative frequencies. After all, if both raters code the same behavior with a very deviant prevalence this might point towards a fundamental problem with the code descriptions or the training. Therefore, we advise checking the agreement of relative frequencies by forehand. In the most general condition, being '1's and '0's are equally likely ($p_1(1)=p_2(1)=p_1(0)=p_2(0)=.5$), the chance agreement for all three interrater agreement measure calculates to .5.

Table 2.1.
Formula and selected values of the correction term for Brennan-Prediger coefficient, Cohen's Kappa, and Gwet's AC

Name	Correction term	$p_1(1)=p_2(1)=.5$ $p_1(0)=p_2(0)=.5$	$p_1(1)=p_2(1)=.1$ $p_1(0)=p_2(0)=.9$
Brennan-Prediger coefficient	.5 (two categories)	.5	.5
Cohen's Kappa	$P_e = p_1(1)p_2(1) + p_1(0)p_2(0)$.5	.82
Gwet's AC	$e(\gamma) = 2 \cdot \frac{p_1(1) + p_2(1)}{2} \cdot \frac{p_1(0) + p_2(0)}{2}$.5	.18

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Appendix 3 – Study 3: Investigating the impact of the error pattern

In the main section, we described an error pattern shuffling approach that cuts the segments without taking into account whether the candidate changing points will hit on 1s and change them into 0s or vice versa. This might reflect the truth in that influences like fatigue or distraction might lay on the base of the miscoding and these influences are tied to the coder and do not account for what happens in the videotaped interaction at that moment.

Alternative error pattern generation

There are, however, two arguments that question this paradigm. First, changing time points without regarding the content (1s or 0s) might change the relative frequency in the simulated data: in true data with a low relative frequency, it is more likely that 0s are changed to 1s which will lead to a higher relative frequency of the generated rater data. Second, the raters themselves might be biased and make a higher percentage of errors in one score. To this end, we executed other simulation studies in which we used a slightly different implementation of error (see Fig A3.1). This approach allows monitoring of how many errors are committed in 1s and 0s respectively. We do so by applying the segment shuffling approach independently on both types of scores.

Figure A3.1. A shuffling approach that allows varying the percentage of candidates changing points for a score

Note: Step 1. The true data is sorted in a time series containing all 1s and one containing all 0s. Step 2. The overall number of changed points is calculated (by multiplying the error rate with the overall length of the time series).

Step 3. The number of candidate change points is split into two groups following a predetermined percentage (here we used 50%). Step 4. The segment shuffling procedure is now applied on each of the two time series separately (the length of the segments is the same, which means that the number of segments may vary between the two time series but sums up to the same number as in the random approach – see Fig X). Step 5. The indicated points are changed in the true data.

Simulation Study

In this simulation study we completely crossed the following manipulations (see Appendix 1)

- Relative frequency of the true data: p_1^{true} : .1, .2, .3, .4, .5
- Serial dependency in the true data: $p_{1|1}^{true}$: none (i.e., $p_{1|1}^{true} = p_1^{true}$), .5, .6, .7, .8, .9⁸
- Relative frequency in the error (error rate): .053, .113, .184
- Serial dependency in the error: segments of 1, 5, or 20 time points length

We executed this simulation study for three different percentages. In the first simulation study, we assumed that the raters made equally many mistakes in coding behavior than in coding the absence of behavior (50%). In the other two studies, 1/3 of the errors were committed in the 1s and 2/3 of the errors were committed in the 1s respectively.

Simulation study 3.1: Committed errors are evenly distributed: between the 1s and 0s

Figure A3.2.

Cohen's Kappa as functions of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and committed errors, which is evenly likely to occur at time points with true behavior or without.

⁸ Please note that for $p_1^{true}=.5$ the value $p_{1|1}^{true} = 0.5$ equals the non serial dependency condition.

Note: a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (segment length of 1 time point) and b) presence of a moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (segments are 5 time points long) c) strong serial dependence in the committed errors (segments have a length of 20 time points). Within each panel, each group of vertical lines represents the same true relative frequency as indicated on the x-axis and the same error relative frequency (yellow:0.053, orange:0.113, red: 0.184). The different lines within each group represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (none, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9). Each vertical line indicates the range of the results (with a fixed relative frequency, serial dependency, and error rate), while the horizontal dash marks the mean of the results.

Simulation study 3.2: Committed errors are distributed asymmetrically: 1/3 committed in the shown behaviors, 2/3 in absent behaviors.

Figure A3.3. Cohen's Kappa as functions of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and committed errors, of which 33% is committed at time points with true behavior.

Note: a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (segment length of 1 time point) and b) presence of a moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (segments are 5 time points long) c) strong serial dependence in the committed errors (segments have a length of 20 time points). Within each panel, each group of

vertical lines represents the same true relative frequency as indicated on the x-axis and the same error relative frequency (yellow:0.053, orange:0.113, red: 0.184). The different lines within each group represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (none, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9). Each vertical line indicates the range of the results (with a fixed relative frequency, serial dependency, and error rate), while the horizontal dash marks the mean of the results.

Simulation study 3.3: Committed errors are distributed asymmetrically: 2/3 committed in the shown behaviors, 1/3 in absent behaviors.

Figure A3.4.

Cohen’s Kappa as functions of the relative frequency and serial dependency of both the true behavior and committed errors, of which 67% is committed at time points with true behavior.

Note: a) Absence of serial dependency in the committed errors (segment length of 1 time point) and b) presence of a moderate serial dependency in the committed errors (segments are 5 time points long) c) strong serial dependence in the committed errors (segments have a length of 20 time points). Within each panel, each group of vertical lines represents the same true relative frequency as indicated on the x-axis and the same error relative frequency (yellow:0.053, orange:0.113, red: 0.184). The different lines within each group represent different amounts of serial dependency in the true data (none, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9). Each vertical line indicates the range of the results (with a fixed relative frequency, serial dependency, and error rate), while the horizontal dash marks the mean of the results.

Appendix 4: Benchmarks and error rate

In this paragraph, we aim to bring back the interpretation of interrater agreement values to a more pivotal measure of agreement: the error rate. As an error rate, we consider the number of errors that one rater committed on the true data during the rating process. The committed errors of course have a direct impact on the agreement between the raters, the agreement will never be smaller than one minus the sum of errors committed though both raters together. It might, however, be bigger, as time points that are misspecified by both raters are counted as agreement.

To allow the comparison with previous studies and to satisfy the need to distinguish different levels of agreement, we will relate the error rates to the benchmarks (we concentrate here on those of Landis & Koch). As an example, we calculate in what follows the error rate that would correspond to a value for Cohen's kappa of .6 (indicating the Landis & Koch benchmark between moderate and substantial agreement):

We assume that the benchmarks were constructed for the most general case of data in which the relative frequency of both variables is .5 (i.e., the scores of 0 and 1 are equally likely) and no serial dependence is present.

In this special case, the correction for chance agreement of Cohen's kappa is .5:

$$P_e = p_1(1)p_2(1) + p_1(0)p_2(0) = .5 * .5 + .5 * .5 = .5$$

If we now fill out the formula for Cohen's Kappa with a correction term value of .5 and a wanted value for Cohen's kappa of .6. We can trace back the steps and calculate the value for the proportion of agreement.

$$\frac{P_a - .5}{.5} = .6 \Rightarrow P_a = .8$$

This value of agreement of .8 corresponds to a disagreement of .2 This disagreement is composed by the time points where rater 1 makes an error, but rater 2 does not or vice versa and can thus be calculated using the probabilities p_1^{err} (rater 1 makes a mistake) and p_2^{err} (rater 2 makes a mistake):

$$p_1^{err}(1 - p_2^{err}) + (1 - p_1^{err}) * p_2^{err} = .2$$

$$p_1^{err} - p_1^{err} p_2^{err} + p_2^{err} - p_1^{err} p_2^{err} = .2$$

As we assume that the errors committed by rater 1 and 2 are equal we get:

$$2 * p^{err} - 2 * (p^{err})^2 = .2$$

$$(p^{err})^2 - p^{err} + .1 = 0$$

Using the formula to solve quadratic equations we can figure out that this is true for $p^{err} = \frac{-1 \pm \sqrt{1^2 - 4 * 1 * .1}}{2} \approx .1127$ (the other result of 0.8873 is not retained because the agreement here mainly comes from both raters committing so many errors that some of them occur at the same time which is not the situation we wanted to consider here). This means that with an error rate of 11.3% for each rater the expected interrater data value complies with .6. If we do the same calculations for the benchmarks of .8 and .4, error rates are 5.3% and 18.4% respectively.

Appendix 5: Type 1 error & Power for a test with original/segmented data generation approach

Figure 5.1. Type 1 error for the test with an error rate of 5.3% and 11.3% in dependence of the length of the time series, the relative frequency, and the serial dependence.

Note: Type 1 error for the test with an error rate of 5.3% (left column) and 11.3% (right column). The results depict the percentage of rater data pairs that were erroneously classified as significantly higher than would be expected. The error rate in the rater data and in the test are the same. Different rows depict different time series lengths (50,100,200, 500 time points), within each panel different relative frequencies (.1, .2, .3, .4, .5; x-axis) and serial dependency conditions (symbols & line type) are used. For each condition, 1000 pairs of rater data were generated and tested with a sampling distribution of 500 values. The sampling distribution is generated using the original approach.

Figure 5.2. Type 1 error for the test with an error rate of 5.3% and 11.3% in dependence of the length of the time series, the relative frequency, and the serial dependence.

Note: Type 1 error for the test with an error rate of 5.3% (left column) and 11.3% (right column). The results depict the percentage of rater data pairs that were erroneously classified as significantly higher than would be expected. The error rate in the rater data and in the test are the same. Different rows depict different time series lengths (50,100,200, 500 time points), within each panel different relative frequencies (.1, .2, .3, .4, .5; x-axis) and serial dependency conditions (symbols & line type) are used. For each condition, 1000 pairs of rater data were generated and tested with a sampling distribution of 500 values. The sampling distribution is generated using the segmented approach.

Figure 5.3. Power for the test with an error rate of 5.3% in dependence of the error rate in the data (depending on the length of the time series, the relative frequency, and the serial dependence).

Note: Power for the test with an error rate of 5.3%. The results depict the percentage of rater data pairs that were correctly classified as significantly higher than would be expected. Different columns depict different relative frequencies in the true data frequencies (.1, .2, .3, .4, .5). Different rows depict different time series lengths (50,100,200, 500 time points), within each panel different error rates (.01, .02, .03, .04, .053; x-axis) and serial dependency conditions (symbols & line type) are used. For each condition, 1000 pairs of rater data were generated and tested with a sampling distribution of 500 values. The sampling distribution is generated using the original approach

Figure 5.4. Power for the test with an error rate of 5.3% in dependence of the error rate in the data (depending on the length of the time series, the relative frequency, and the serial dependence).

Note: Power for the test with an error rate of 5.3%. The results depict the percentage of rater data pairs that were correctly classified as significantly higher than would be expected. Different columns depict different relative frequencies in the true data frequencies (.1, .2, .3, .4, .5). Different rows depict different time series lengths (50,100,200, 500 time points), within each panel different error rates (.01, .02, .03, .04, .053; x-axis) and serial dependency conditions (symbols & line type) are used. For each condition, 1000 pairs of rater data were generated and tested with a sampling distribution of 500 values. The sampling distribution is generated using the segmented approach

Figure 5.5. Power for the test with an error rate of 11.3% in dependence of the error rate in the data (depending on the length of the time series, the relative frequency, and the serial dependence).

Note: Power for the test with an error rate of 11.3%. The results depict the percentage of rater data pairs that were correctly classified as significantly higher than would be expected. Different columns depict different relative frequencies in the true data frequencies (.1, .2, .3, .4, .5). Different rows depict different time series lengths (50,100,200, 500 time points), within each panel different error rates (.05, .06, .07, .08, .09, .10, .113; x-axis) and serial dependency conditions (symbols & line type) are used. For each condition, 1000 pairs of rater data were generated and tested with a sampling distribution of 500 values. The sampling distribution is generated using the original approach.

Figure 5.6. Power for the test with an error rate of 11.3% in dependence of the error rate in the data (depending on the length of the time series, the relative frequency, and the serial dependence).

Note: Power for the test with an error rate of 11.3%. The results depict the percentage of rater data pairs that were correctly classified as significantly higher than would be expected. Different columns depict different relative frequencies in the true data frequencies (.1, .2, .3, .4, .5). Different rows depict different time series lengths (50,100,200, 500 time points), within each panel different error rates (.05, .06, .07, .08, .09, .10, .113; x-axis) and serial dependency conditions (symbols & line type) are used. For each condition, 1000 pairs of rater data were generated and tested with a sampling distribution of 500 values. The sampling distribution is generated using the segmented approach.